

*Study no. 1 for PAM and MADI*

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Study no. 1 for PAM and MADI explores a machine aesthetic. Rather than attempting to replicate the intricacies of human performance, the work emphasizes the novel musical capabilities of these machines. This composition features complex rhythmic relationships, rapid changes in density and timbre, and dynamic contrast. It consists of three sections. The first and third sections use PAM, MADI and computer audio, while the second is an intimate exploration of MADI.

Study no. 1 for PAM and MADI was written by EMMI (Expressive Machines Musical Instruments) co-founders Steven Kemper, Scott Barton, Troy Rogers to commemorate the birth of MADI (multi-Mallet Automatic Drumming Instrument) and PAM's (Poly-tangent Automatic multi-Monochord) first birthday.